

On the Smarandache function and the divisor product sequences

Mingdong Xiao

Department of Mathematics, Northwest University, Xi'an, Shaanxi, P.R.China

Abstract Let n be any positive integer, $P_d(n)$ denotes the product of all positive divisors of n . The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary and analytic methods to study the mean value properties of a new arithmetical function $S(P_d(n))$, and give an interesting asymptotic formula for it.

Keywords Smarandach function, Divisor product sequences, Composite function, mean value, Asymptotic formula.

§1. Introduction

For any positive integer n , the famous F.Smarandache function $S(n)$ is defined as the smallest positive integer m such that n divide $m!$. That is, $S(n) = \min\{m : m \in N, n|m!\}$. And the Smarandache divisor product sequences $\{P_d(n)\}$ is defined as the product of all positive divisors of n . That is, $P_d(n) = \prod_{d|n} d = n^{\frac{d(n)}{2}}$, where $d(n)$ is the Dirichlet divisor function.

For examples, $P_d(1) = 1, P_d(2) = 2, P_d(3) = 3, P_d(4) = 8, \dots$. In problem 25 of reference [1], Professor F.Smarandache asked us to study the properties of the function $S(n)$ and the sequence $\{P_d(n)\}$. About these problems, many scholars had studied them, and obtained a series interesting results, see references [2], [3], [4], [5] and [6]. But at present, none had studied the mean value properties of the composite function $S(P_d(n))$, at least we have not seen any related papers before. In this paper, we shall use the elementary methods to study the mean value properties of $S(P_d(n))$, and give an interesting asymptotic formula for it. That is, we shall prove the following conclusion:

Theorem. For any fixed positive integer k and any real number $x \geq 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} S(P_d(n)) = \frac{\pi^4}{72} \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k b_i \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where b_i ($i = 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

§2. Some simple lemmas

To complete the proof of the theorem, we need the following several simple lemmas. First we have

Lemma 1. For any positive integer α , we have the estimate

$$S(p^\alpha) \leq \alpha p.$$

Especially, when $\alpha \leq p$, we have $S(p^\alpha) = \alpha p$, where p is a prime.

Proof. See reference [3].

Lemma 2. For any positive integer n , let $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_k^{\alpha_k}$ denotes the factorization of n into prime powers, then we have

$$S(n) = \max_{1 \leq i \leq k} \{S(p_i^{\alpha_i})\}.$$

Lemma 3. Let $P(n)$ denotes the greatest prime divisor of n , if $P(n) > \sqrt{n}$, then we have $S(n) = P(n)$.

Proof. The proof of Lemma 2 and Lemma 3 can be found in reference [4].

§3. Proof of the theorem

In this section, we shall use the above lemmas to complete the proof of our theorem. For any positive integer n , it is clear that from the definition of $P_d(n)$ we have

$$P_d^2(n) = \left(\prod_{r|n} r \right) \cdot \left(\prod_{r|n} \frac{n}{r} \right) = n^{\sum_{r|n} 1} = n^{d(n)}.$$

So we have the identity $P_d(n) = n^{\frac{d(n)}{2}}$. Let $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_k^{\alpha_k}$ denotes the factorization of n into prime powers. First we separate all integers n in the interval $[1, x]$ into two subsets A and B as follows:

$$A = \{n : n \leq x, P(n) \leq \sqrt{n}\}, \quad B = \{n : n \leq x, P(n) > \sqrt{n}\}.$$

If $n \in A$, then from Lemma 1 and Lemma 2, and note that $P_d(n) = n^{\frac{d(n)}{2}}$ we have

$$P_d(n) = n^{\frac{d(n)}{2}} = p_1^{\frac{\alpha_1 d(n)}{2}} p_2^{\frac{\alpha_2 d(n)}{2}} \cdots p_k^{\frac{\alpha_k d(n)}{2}}.$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} S(P_d(n)) &= S \left(p_1^{\frac{\alpha_1 d(n)}{2}} p_2^{\frac{\alpha_2 d(n)}{2}} \cdots p_k^{\frac{\alpha_k d(n)}{2}} \right) = \max_{1 \leq i \leq k} \left\{ S \left(p_i^{\frac{\alpha_i d(n)}{2}} \right) \right\} \\ &\leq \max_{1 \leq i \leq k} \left\{ \frac{\alpha_i d(n)}{2} p_i \right\} \leq \frac{d(n)}{2} \sqrt{n} \ln n. \end{aligned}$$

From reference [10] we know that

$$\sum_{n \leq x} d(n) = x \ln x + O(x).$$

So we have the estimate

$$\sum_{n \in A} S(P_d(n)) \leq \sum_{n \in A} \frac{d(n)}{2} \sqrt{n} \ln n \ll \sum_{n \leq x} d(n) \sqrt{x} \ln x \ll x^{\frac{3}{2}} \ln^2 x. \tag{1}$$

If $n \in B$, let $n = n_1 p$, where $n_1 < \sqrt{n} < p$. It is clear that $d(n_1) < \sqrt{n} < p$ and $d(n) = 2d(n_1)$. So from Lemma 3 we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \in B} S(P_d(n)) &= \sum_{\substack{n_1 p \leq x \\ n_1 < p}} S\left((n_1 p) \frac{d(n_1 p)}{2}\right) = \sum_{\substack{n_1 p \leq x \\ n_1 < p}} S\left(p \frac{d(n_1 p)}{2}\right) \\ &= \sum_{n \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{n < p \leq \frac{x}{n}} d(n) p = \sum_{n \leq \sqrt{x}} d(n) \sum_{n < p \leq \frac{x}{n}} p \\ &= \sum_{n \leq \sqrt{x}} d(n) \sum_{p \leq \frac{x}{n}} p + O\left(\sum_{n \leq \sqrt{x}} d(n) \cdot \frac{n}{\ln n}\right) \\ &= \sum_{n \leq \sqrt{x}} d(n) \sum_{p \leq \frac{x}{n}} p + O(x). \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

From the Abel's summation formula (see Theorem 4.2 of [10]) and the Prime Theorem (see Theorem 3.2 of [11]) we have

$$\pi(x) = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{a_i \cdot x}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where a_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$) are computable constants and $a_1 = 1$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{p \leq \frac{x}{n}} p &= \frac{x}{n} \pi\left(\frac{x}{n}\right) - \int_2^{\frac{x}{n}} \pi(y) dy \\ &= \frac{x^2}{2n^2 \ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{c_i \cdot x^2 \ln^i n}{n^2 \ln^2 x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{n^2 \ln^{k+1} x}\right), \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where c_i ($i = 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

Note that

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$$

and

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{d(n)}{n^2} = \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2}\right)^2 = \frac{\pi^4}{36}, \tag{4}$$

from (2), (3) and (4) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \in B} S(P_d(n)) &= \frac{x^2}{2 \ln x} \sum_{n \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{d(n)}{n^2} + \sum_{n \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{c_i \cdot x^2 d(n) \ln^i n}{n^2 \ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right) \\ &= \frac{\pi^4}{72} \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k b_i \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where b_i ($i = 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

Now combining (1) and (5) we may immediately get the asymptotic formula

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} S(P_d(n)) &= \sum_{n \in A} S(P_d(n)) + \sum_{n \in B} S(P_d(n)) \\ &= \frac{\pi^4}{72} \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k b_i \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right), \end{aligned}$$

where b_i ($i = 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants. This completes the proof of Theorem.

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